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“WHEN LOVE WAS THE REAL QUESTION”

I saw the two of you so sweet,
as if the world had left your feet;
you laughed so freely, bright and loud,
lost together inside the crowd.

I saw you there, and you saw me,
yet still you smiled too carelessly;
you knew the wound that sight would start,
but acted calm and hid your heart.

You said I doubted you too much,
that I should speak and not lose touch;
you placed the blame on my young mind,
as if my pain were being blind.

But the issue was never trust,
nor tears that turned my faith to dust;
if love still lived inside your heart,
you would not have played that part.

So let the truth rise from the rust,
the problem was never trust.